

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Fate of Patients with Solitary Pulmonary Nodules: Clinical Management and Radiation Exposure Associated

Blanca Lumbreras^{1,2*}, José Vilar³, Isabel González-Álvarez⁴, Noemí Gómez-Sáez¹, María L. Domingo³, María F. Lorente⁴, María Pastor-Valero^{1,2}, Ildefonso Hernández-Aguado^{1,2}

1 Public Health Department, Miguel Hernández University, Alicante, Spain, **2** CIBER en Epidemiología y Salud Pública, Madrid, Spain, **3** Radiodiagnostic Department, Peset Hospital, Valencia, Spain, **4** Radiodiagnostic Department, San Juan Hospital, Alicante, Spain

* blumbreras@umh.es

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Lumbreras B, Vilar J, González-Álvarez I, Gómez-Sáez N, Domingo ML, Lorente MF, et al. (2016) The Fate of Patients with Solitary Pulmonary Nodules: Clinical Management and Radiation Exposure Associated. PLoS ONE 11(7): e0158458. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458

Editor: William B. Coleman, University of North Carolina School of Medicine, UNITED STATES

Received: December 20, 2015

Accepted: June 16, 2016

Published: July 8, 2016

Copyright: © 2016 Lumbreras et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Data Availability Statement: All relevant data are within the paper and its Supporting Information files.

Funding: This study has received funding by Instituto de Salud Carlos III (Minister of Science, Spain) (Ref. PI09/0477) and and co-funded by the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER).

Competing Interests: These funding organizations have not participated in the design and conduct of the study; collection, management, analysis, and interpretation of the data; and preparation, review, or

Abstract

Background

The appropriate management of the large number of lung nodules detected during the course of routine medical care presents a challenge. We aimed to evaluate the usual clinical practice in solitary pulmonary nodule (SPN) management and associated radiation exposure.

Methods

We examined 893 radiology reports of consecutive patients undergoing chest computed tomography (CT) and radiography at two public hospitals in Spain. Information on diagnostic procedures from SPN detection and lung cancer diagnosis was collected prospectively for 18 months.

Results

More than 20% of patients with SPN detected on either chest radiograph (19.8%) or CT (26.1%) underwent no additional interventions and none developed lung cancer (100% negative predictive value). 346 (72.0%) patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph and 254 (61.5%) patients with SPN detected on CT had additional diagnostic tests and were not diagnosed with lung cancer. In patients undergoing follow-up imaging for SPNs detected on CT median number of additional imaging tests was 3.5 and the mean cumulative effective dose was 24.4 mSv; for those detected on chest radiograph the median number of additional imaging tests was 2.8 and the mean cumulative effective dose was 10.3 mSv.

Conclusions

Patients who did not have additional interventions were not diagnosed of lung cancer. There was an excessive amount of interventions in a high percentage of patients presenting SPN, which was associated with an excess of radiation exposure.

approval of the manuscript; and decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

Introduction

A large number of lung nodules are detected during the course of routine medical care and their appropriate management presents a challenge [1]. There is sufficient evidence of the negative consequences stemming from poorly targeted investigations [2–7]. However, there is no evidence about the exposure to radiation during the management of a pulmonary nodule, defined as a pulmonary opacity up to 30 millimetres in diameter [8].

Given the natural history of lung cancer, clinicians tend to adopt a proactive attitude performing clinical interventions that are often unnecessary [9]. Recently, the British Thoracic Society (BTS) has published guidelines for the management of pulmonary nodules [10]. These guidelines present the most up to date and evidence based recommendations for follow up, although most of these recommendations are classified as Grade C or D. Moreover, in contrast with Fleischner recommendations [11] and in agreement with the latest information from the NELSON trial, [12] they do not recommend follow-up for people with nodules <5 mm in maximum diameter.

A recently published retrospective study on 300 adults with pulmonary nodules from 15 Veterans Affairs hospitals reveals that pulmonary nodule evaluation is often inconsistent with the Fleischner Society guidelines [13]. Moreover, there is some data that shows marked variability in the management of SPN detected on CT in usual clinical practice [14]. A recent study focused on patients with intermediate-sized nodules who were referred to community-based pulmonologists, showed that 44% of low-risk patients underwent one or more invasive procedures for a benign nodule [15].

New guidelines in the SPN management have been published. However, given that the majority of research studies involving pulmonary nodules are in screened populations [16–19], there is a need to evaluate the management of SPNs detected on imaging studies ordered for a number of reasons in the general clinical setting. The evaluation of the impact of these different management strategies carried out in patients with SPN on the diagnosis of lung cancer in a routine setting would be an essential guide for clinicians. In addition, the measurement of the radiation exposure associated with different clinical pathways could be useful when making clinical decisions.

Therefore, the aim of this prospective study was to describe the management of SPN detected on both chest radiograph and CT scans performed in routine practice including variables associated with management decisions, final diagnoses and total radiation exposure.

Material and Methods

Study subjects

During the years 2010 and 2011, all patients ≥ 35 years free of lung cancer referred for thoracic imaging evaluation in two general public hospitals in the Valencian Community (Spain) were prospectively collected from the radiological electronic record (a total of 25,529 patients). Eight expert radiologists working in the radiologist departments at the time in both hospitals determined the presence of SPN in the thoracic study of these patients (a total of 893 (3.5%) out of 25,529 examined) [20]. Information on diagnostic procedures from SPN discovery and lung cancer diagnosis was collected prospectively for 18 months. In these 893 patients with SPN detected, the risk of developing lung cancer in an 18 month follow-up period was nearly 10% [21]. The target population of the present study consisted of the residents of the catchment area of the participating public hospitals: San Juan Hospital and Dr Peset Hospital, with a catchment population of 234,424 and 377,780 people, respectively. The two hospitals belong to the National Health Care System and are referral hospitals for all individuals living in the same

geographical area. The majority of the population in these areas uses the National Health Care System as the main medical service.

Institutional Review Board approval (University Miguel Hernandez Committee Ref DSP-BLL-001-10) was obtained. Given the study uses only routine data and no additional interventions, informed consent was not sought from the patients and this was approved by the IRB. Patient information was anonymized and participants' identification code numbers were de-identified by replacing the original code number with a new random code number.

Data collection

Patients were classified into two groups according to the initial imaging exam on which the SPN was identified: chest radiograph or CT.

Detection and description of the SPN. Eight chest expert radiologists (all of them with more than 10 years of experience) determined the presence of SPN in thoracic studies of the 25,529 patients initially included. We limited our study to nodules between and 30 millimeters [8]. Intrapulmonary lymph nodes and pseudolesions, when detected, were excluded from our study.

Chest radiographs were obtained with the standard technique in digital format (CR Philips). The CT technique varied according to the study that was being performed. CT imaging tests were obtained with slice thicknesses of 3mm or less (2 mm, 1.5 and 1.25) according to the different clinical situations and the equipment used, 120 KvP and variable mAs. The nodules were measured using calipers in the PACS workstations in their largest diameter in the posterior anterior and lateral radiograph. CT lung window settings (1550/-600) were used to measure nodule size in the largest diameter. Mediastinal window settings (350/50) were also used to further detect calcification or fat (<40 Hounsfield units) within the nodule.

The radiologists described nodule characteristics in a predesigned form consisting of: a) size, in mms, and also expressed as mean (sd) in diameter; b) nodule shape, smooth or irregular (lobular or spiculated); c) location, and d) for those patients who underwent a CT, nodule consistency (solid, partly solid, ground glass, calcification or not specified). As we previously reported [20], for the evaluation of inter-observer agreement in particular aspects such as nodule size, shape or consistency, the first 300 tests included were evaluated independently by the 8 radiologists. For the intra-observer agreement of these characteristics, the radiologists re-evaluated 200 studies at least 6 months after the first report. In case of discordance, the consensus was established by the 2 radiologists with more experience (IGA and JV).

Patients' characteristics. Selected clinical and demographic variables were gathered from the medical records for all patients: type of test performed; department that ordered the test; care setting; reason for test and patient characteristics. Moreover, we collected from the medical records: smoking status, previous neoplasm, presence of a respiratory disease and respiratory symptoms.

Follow-up

Prospective follow-up during 18 months was conducted in all 893 patients through the review of their medical records, including the ascertainment of lung cancer diagnosis and the specific cause of death (if they occurred).

All the additional interventions carried out were collected on a pre-established form. Based on Fleischner Society Criteria [11] of a three-month interval for follow-up imaging, immediate intervention was defined as any study performed within a three month window following SPN identification and additional imaging was defined as any imaging study performed at or beyond three months form SPN identification.

In those patients who underwent CT as an additional or immediate intervention, we distinguished between those patients who underwent 1 CT (labelled in the results section as 'CT') and those who underwent 1 or more follow-up CT three months after the previous test was carried out (labelled in the results section as 'CT surveillance'). A diagnosis of lung cancer was confirmed by cytopathological evaluation of needle-aspiration biopsy samples or histopathologic examination of surgically resected specimens [22]. Tissue was always obtained from the primary lung lesions.

We estimated the cumulative effective dose of diagnostic procedures in the study population according to previous evidence [23]: chest radiograph (0.1 mSv), chest CT (7 mSv), PET/CT (25 mSv). We compared the effective doses received in those patients who ascertained a diagnosis of lung cancer and those who did not.

Statistical analysis

All data was computerized and checked to discard errors. Statistical precision was determined through the calculation of 95% CI. All analyses were carried out with the statistical programme Stata 8 (Stata Corp., College Station, Texas, USA).

A descriptive analysis was performed to estimate the proportions of the patients and nodule characteristics according to the immediate next step in management (immediate intervention vs additional imaging studies or no further work up not further working). A descriptive analysis was carried out using frequency distribution or median and interquartile range (IQR) when appropriate. The age was transformed in quartiles because the equal variance and normal distribution was rejected. Nodule diameter was categorized according to Fleischner recommendations.

Results

[Fig 1](#) illustrates the lung cancer incidence and specific mortality in the 893 patients with SPN during the 18 months of follow-up. Clinicians decided to perform immediate interventions in 410 patients (45.9%); follow-up in 280 cases (31.3%) and in 203 patients (22.7%) clinicians decided not test further. The diverse management strategies carried out in patients having SPN for both imaging tests and the detailed description of the diagnostic pathway is given in [S1](#) and [S2](#) Text, [S1](#) and [S2](#) Figs. In our study, there were no patients who underwent invasive procedures (including CT guided biopsy, bronchoscopy, or surgery) as the immediate next test following SPN identification. In brief:

Diagnostic pathway ([Table 1](#))

Not tested further. 95 (19.8%) out of 480 patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph and 108 (26.2%) out of 413 patients with SPN detected on CT were not further tested and none of them were diagnosed with lung cancer during the 18 month-follow-up study. Most of them were benign granuloma.

Follow-up three months after the detection of SPN. Out of 84 (17.5%) patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph, 35 (41.7%) were followed up with chest radiograph, 48 (57.1%) with CT and 1 (1.2%) with PET/CT. Four (4.8%) patients were diagnosed with lung cancer (median time to diagnosis: 9 months; IQR 7–11 months). Out of 196 (47.5%) patients with SPN detected on CT, 18 (9.2%), were followed up with chest radiograph, 175 (89.3%) with CT (89.3%) and 3 (1.5%) with PET/CT. Eleven (5.6%) patients were diagnosed with lung cancer (median time to diagnosis: 7 months; IQR 6–12 months).

Immediate intervention. Out of 301 (62.7%) patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph, 67 (22.3%) had immediate interventions with chest radiograph, 225 (78.4%) with CT

Fig 1. Flow diagram showing the follow-up of the study participants.

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.g001

and 29 (12.9%) with PET/CT and 36 (11.9%) patients were diagnosed with lung cancer (median time to diagnosis: 2 months; IQR 1–4 months). 109 (26.4%) patients with SPN detected on CT had immediate interventions with chest radiograph (3, 2.7%), CT (20, 18.3%) or PET/CT (47, 43.1%). 40 (36.7%) patients were diagnosed with lung cancer (median time to diagnosis: 0.8 months; IQR 0.3–1.5 months).

Table 1. Description of patient's characteristics according to the clinical management strategy after the detection of a SPN (for chest radiograph and CT) and lung cancer diagnosis after 18 months of follow-up*.

VARIABLES	Chest radiograph		CT		p-value	Immediate interventions 301 (62.7%) (lung cancer 36; 11.9%)	Follow-up 84 (17.5%) (lung cancer 4; 4.8%)	No further testing 95 (19.8%) (lung cancer 0)	Total 413 (lung cancer 51; 12.4%)	No further testing 108 (26.2%) (lung cancer 0)	Follow-up 196 (47.5%) (lung cancer 11; 5.6%)	Immediate interventions 109 (26.4%) (lung cancer 40; 36.7%)	p-value
	N (%)	(95% CI)	N (%)	(95% CI)									
Gender					0.000								0.191
Male	285		36 (12.6) (2; 5.5)	198 (69.5) 27 (13.6)		198 (69.5) 27 (13.6)	36 (12.6) (2; 5.5)	51 (17.9)	261	72 (27.6)	115 (44.1) (9; 7.8)	74 (28.4) (34; 45.9)	
Female	195		48 (24.6) (2; 4.2)	103 (52.8) (9; 8.7)		103 (52.8) (9; 8.7)	48 (24.6) (2; 4.2)	44 (22.6)	152	36 (23.7)	81 (53.3) (2; 2.5)	35 (23.0) (6; 17.1)	
Age in years					0.056								0.055
< 50	76		7 (9.2) (1; 14.3)	51 (67.1) (2; 3.9)		51 (67.1) (2; 3.9)	7 (9.2) (1; 14.3)	18 (23.7)	50	16 (32.0)	22 (44.0) (1; 4.5)	12 (24.0) (5; 41.7)	
50–59	86		22 (25.6) (2; 9.1)	52 (60.5) (10; 19.2)		52 (60.5) (10; 19.2)	22 (25.6) (2; 9.1)	12 (14.0)	87	12 (13.8)	45 (51.7) (2; 4.4)	30 (34.5) (8; 26.7)	
60–69	132		23 (17.4) (0)	89 (67.4) (11; 12.4)		89 (67.4) (11; 12.4)	23 (17.4) (0)	20 (15.2)	126	31 (24.6)	64 (50.8) (4; 6.3)	31 (24.6) (12; 38.7)	
≥70	186		32 (17.2) (1; 3.1)	109 (58.6) (13; 11.9)		109 (58.6) (13; 11.9)	32 (17.2) (1; 3.1)	45 (24.2)	150	49 (32.7)	65 (43.3) (4; 6.2)	36 (24.0) (15; 31.7)	
Reason for requesting imaging test					0.696								0.662
Preoperative	86		17 (19.8) (0)	48 (55.8) (10; 20.8)		48 (55.8) (10; 20.8)	17 (19.8) (0)	21 (24.4)	80	21 (26.3)	34 (42.5) (1; 2.9)	25 (31.3) (11; 44.0)	
Respiratory	135		25 (18.5) (1; 4.0)	87 (64.4) (9; 10.3)		87 (64.4) (9; 10.3)	25 (18.5) (1; 4.0)	23 (17.0)	85	28 (32.9)	37 (43.5) (1; 2.7)	20 (23.5) (9; 45.0)	
Non-respiratory	102		20 (19.6) (2; 10.0)	64 (62.8) (9; 14.1)		64 (62.8) (9; 14.1)	20 (19.6) (2; 10.0)	18 (17.7)	108	30 (27.8)	51 (47.2) (6; 11.7)	27 (25.0) (9; 33.3)	
Extra pulmonary neoplasm	50		7 (14.0) (0)	35 (70.0) (3; 8.6)		35 (70.0) (3; 8.6)	7 (14.0) (0)	8 (16.0)	51	10 (19.6)	27 (52.9) (2; 7.4)	14 (27.5) (5; 35.7)	
Not specified	107		15 (14.0) (1; 6.7)	67 (62.6) (5; 7.5)		67 (62.6) (5; 7.5)	15 (14.0) (1; 6.7)	25 (23.4)	89	19 (21.4)	47 (52.8) (1; 2.1)	23 (25.8) (6; 26.1)	
Smoking status					0.462								0.183
Never	99		18 (18.2) (0)	59 (59.6) (2; 3.5)		59 (59.6) (2; 3.5)	18 (18.2) (0)	22 (22.2)	92	28 (30.4)	45 (48.9) (1; 2.2)	19 (20.7) (1; 5.3)	
Ever	275		44 (16.0) (4; 9.1)	182 (66.2) (31; 17.0)		182 (66.2) (31; 17.0)	44 (16.0) (4; 9.1)	49 (17.8)	252	60 (23.8)	115 (45.6) (8; 6.9)	77 (30.6) (39; 50.6)	
Not specified	106		22 (20.8) (0)	60 (56.6) (3; 5.0)		60 (56.6) (3; 5.0)	22 (20.8) (0)	24 (22.6)	69	20 (29.0)	36 (52.2) (2; 5.6)	13 (18.8) (0)	
Previous malignancy					0.066								0.891
No	313		48 (15.3) (2; 4.2)	195 (62.3) (21; 10.8)		195 (62.3) (21; 10.8)	48 (15.3) (2; 4.2)	70 (22.4)	286	75 (26.2)	135 (47.2) (7; 5.2)	76 (26.6) (28; 36.8)	
Yes	167		36 (21.6) (2; 5.6)	106 (63.5) (15; 14.2)		106 (63.5) (15; 14.2)	36 (21.6) (2; 5.6)	25 (15.0)	126	33 (26.2)	60 (47.6) (4; 6.7)	33 (26.2) (12; 36.4)	
Not specified	-		-	-		-	-	-	1	0 (0.0)	1 (0)	0 (0.0)	
COPD					0.378								0.100
No	361		66 (18.3) (3; 4.5)	220 (60.9) (19; 8.6)		220 (60.9) (19; 8.6)	66 (18.3) (3; 4.5)	75 (20.8)	296	80 (27.0)	148 (50.0) (7; 4.7)	68 (23.0) (21; 30.9)	
Yes	119		18 (15.1) (1; 5.6)	81 (68.1) (17; 21.0)		81 (68.1) (17; 21.0)	18 (15.1) (1; 5.6)	20 (16.8)	116	28 (24.1)	47 (40.5) (4; 8.5)	41 (35.3) (19; 46.3)	
Not specified	-		-	-		-	-	-	1	0 (0.0)	1 (0)	0 (0.0)	
Respiratory Symptoms					0.123								0.695
No	404		73 (18.1) (3; 4.1)	246 (60.9) (31; 12.6)		246 (60.9) (31; 12.6)	73 (18.1) (3; 4.1)	85 (21.0)	345	91 (26.4)	163 (47.2) (10; 6.1)	91 (26.4) (35; 38.5)	
Yes	52		9 (17.3) (1; 11.1)	39 (75.0) (4; 10.3)		39 (75.0) (4; 10.3)	9 (17.3) (1; 11.1)	4 (7.7)	57	14 (24.6)	26 (45.6) (1; 3.8)	27 (29.8) (4; 14.8)	
Not specified	24		2 (8.3) (0)	16 (66.7) (1; 6.3)		16 (66.7) (1; 6.3)	2 (8.3) (0)	6 (25.0)	11	3 (27.3)	7 (63.6) (0)	1 (9.1) (1; 100.0)	

(*) Lung cancer cases are shown in bold for each category together with the risk as a percentage.

Determinants of diagnostic pathways

According to [Table 1](#), in patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph, men had more frequently immediate interventions than women (198/285, 69.5% and 103/195, 52.8%, respectively; $p < 0.001$).

In both patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph and CT, immediate interventions were more frequent in patients with a spiculated nodule (41/50, 82.0% and 35/67, 52.2%, respectively) ($p = 0.027$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively). Of those patients who underwent immediate interventions lung cancer was diagnosed in 21 patients with spiculated nodules and 1 patient with a smooth nodule (in patients with SPN initially detected on chest radiograph) and in 20 patients with spiculated nodules and 1 patient with a smooth nodule (in patients with SPN initially detected on CT) ([Table 2](#)).

According to the data presented in [Table 3](#), immediate interventions were more frequent in patients with nodules larger than 8 mm in both situations; patients with SPN detected in chest radiograph and those detected on CT (218/287, 69.9% and 70/188, 37.2%, respectively) ($p < 0.001$). However, lung cancer diagnosis was more frequently diagnosed in patients with nodules larger than 8 mm who underwent follow-up (32.0% patients with SPN detected in chest radiograph and 36.5% patients with SPN detected in CT) ([Table 2](#)).

In multivariate analysis, patients with SPN detected on chest radiographs, men were more likely to have immediate interventions (RR 1.45; CI95% 1.23–1.65; $p = 0.002$). In patients with SPN detected on chest radiographs and CT, spiculated nodules were more likely to have immediate interventions (RR 1.27; CI95% 1.10–1.51; $p = 0.034$, and RR 3.83; CI95% 2.16–6.79; $p < 0.001$, respectively) and patients with nodules larger than 8 mm were more likely to have immediate interventions (RR 2.35; CI95% 1.43–3.83; $p < 0.001$, and RR 2.19; CI95% 1.13–4.22; $p < 0.001$, respectively).

Exposure to radiation

In patients undergoing follow-up imaging for SPNs detected on chest radiograph the mean cumulative effective dose was 10.3 mSv. Those ultimately diagnosed with cancer received a significantly higher radiation dose (19.7 vs 9.1, $p = 0.027$). In those who underwent immediate interventions, the mean cumulative effective dose was 11.6 mSv. Those ultimately diagnosed with cancer received a significantly lower radiation dose (10.4 vs 20.3, $p = 0.003$). ([Table 4](#)).

In patients undergoing follow-up imaging for SPNs detected on CT the mean cumulative effective dose was 24.4 mSv. There was no difference when stratified by diagnosis of cancer. In those who underwent immediate intervention, the mean cumulative effective dose was 24.5 mSv. Those ultimately diagnosed with cancer received a significantly lower radiation dose (20.2 vs 26.7, $p = 0.003$) ([Table 5](#)).

Average number of imaging tests

In patients undergoing follow-up imaging for SPNs detected on chest radiograph the median number of additional imaging tests was 2.8. There was no difference when stratified by diagnosis of cancer. In those who underwent immediate interventions, the median number of imaging tests was 2.7. In this group, those ultimately diagnosed with cancer underwent a significantly higher number of imaging studies (3.4 vs 2.6, $p < 0.001$). ([Table 6](#)).

In patients undergoing follow-up imaging for SPNs detected on CT the median number of additional imaging tests was 3.5. Those ultimately diagnosed with cancer underwent a significantly higher number of imaging studies (4.6 vs 3.4, $p = 0.009$). In those who underwent immediate interventions, the median number of imaging tests was 3.0. In this group, those

Table 2. Description of SPN's characteristics according to the clinical management strategy after the detection of a SPN (for Chest radiograph and CT) and lung cancer diagnosis after 18 months of follow-up*.

VARIABLES	Chest radiograph				CT			
N (%)	No further testing	Follow-up 84	Immediate interventions 301	Total 413 (100%)	No further testing	Follow-up 196	Immediate interventions 109	p-value
(95% CI)	(19.8%)(0)	(17.5%)(4; 4.9%)	(62.7%)(36; 11.9%)	(51; 12.4%)	(26.2%)(0)	(47.5%)(11; 5.6%)	(26.4%)(40; 36.7%)	
Diameter (mm) (median, IQR)	9 (6–15)	10 (6–15)	10 (7–15)	8 (5.4–13)	6.4 (5–10)	7 (5–10)	14 (9.7–20)	0.000
Localization								0.104
Upper lobe	51 (19.4)	49 (18.6)(3; 6.1)	163 (62.0)(28; 17.2)	200	42 (21.0)	99 (49.5)(6; 6.1)	59 (29.5)(25; 42.4)	
Middle lobe	7 (18.4)	9 (23.7)(0)	22 (57.9)(0)	50	25 (50.0)	16 (32.0)(0)	9 (18.0)(1; 11.1)	
Lower lobe	32 (19.9)	22 (13.7)(1; 4.5)	107 (66.5)(7; 6.5)	150	38 (25.3)	73 (48.7)(5; 6.8)	39 (26.0)(14; 38.5)	
Not specified	5 (27.8)	4 (22.2)(0)	9 (50.0)(1; 11.1)	13	3 (23.1)	8 (61.5)(0)	2 (15.4)(0)	0.000
Border								0.027
Smooth border or well defined border	23 (18.1)	19 (15.0)(1; 5.3)	85 (66.9)(1; 1.2)	88	26 (29.6)	50 (56.8)(2; 4.0)	12 (13.6)(1; 8.3)	
Irregular or not well defined								
- Spiculation	4 (8.0)	5 (10.0)(0)	41 (82.0)(21; 51.2)	67	8 (11.9)	24 (35.8)(7; 29.2)	35 (52.2)(20; 57.1)	
- Lobulation	9 (27.3)	3 (9.1)(0)	21 (63.6)(5; 23.8)	41	8 (19.5)	14 (34.2)(1; 7.1)	19 (46.3)(6; 42.1)	
- Other irregular	11 (17.7)	11 (17.7)(2; 18.2)	40 (64.6)(5; 12.5)	44	14 (31.8)	20 (45.5)(0)	10 (22.7)(3; 30.0)	
- Not specified	48 (23.1)	46 (22.1)(1; 2.2)	114 (54.8)(4; 3.5)	173	52 (30.1)	88 (50.9)(1; 1.1)	33 (19.1)(8; 24.2)	0.066
Consistency on CT								
Solid	-	-	-	225	54 (24.0)	118 (52.4)(6; 5.1)	53 (23.6)(17; 32.1)	
Partly solid	-	-	-	14	3 (21.4)	7 (50.0)(1; 14.3)	4 (28.6)(1; 25.0)	
Ground glass	-	-	-	25	6 (24.0)	13 (52.0)(2; 15.4)	6 (24.0)(3; 50.0)	
Calcification	-	-	-	16	4 (25.0)	11 (68.8)(0)	1 (6.3)(0)	
Not specified	-	-	-	133	41 (30.8)	47 (35.3)(2; 4.3)	45 (33.8)(19; 42.2)	

(*) Lung cancer cases are shown in bold for each category together with the risk as a percentage.

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t002

Table 3. Diameter's gradient according to clinical management strategy (for Chest radiograph and CT) and lung cancer diagnosis after 18 months of follow-up*.

VARIABLES	Chest radiograph				CT			
N (%)	No further testing	Follow-up 84	Immediate interventions 301	Total 413 (100%)	No further testing	Follow-up 196	Immediate interventions 109	p-value
(95% CI)	(19.8%)(0)	(17.5%)(4; 4.8%)	(62.7%)(36; 11.9%)	(51; 12.4%)	(26.2%)(0)	(47.5%)(11; 5.6%)	(26.4%)(40; 36.7%)	
Diameter								<0.001
3–4 mm	10 (29.4)	13 (38.2)	11 (32.4)	47	14 (29.8)	25 (53.2)	8 (17.0)	
>4–6	19 (25.7)	23 (31.1)(1; 4.3)	32 (43.2)(1; 2.5)	99	39 (39.4)	45 (45.5)(2; 4.4)	15 (15.2)(3; 20.0)	
>6–8	16 (26.7)	21 (35.0)	23 (38.3)	66	16 (24.2)	38 (57.6)(3; 7.9)	12 (18.2)	
>8	44 (14.1)	25 (8.0)(8; 32)	218 (69.9)(28; 12.8)	188	33 (17.6)	85 (45.2)(31; 36.5)	70 (37.2)(11; 15.7)	
Not specified	6 (24.0)	2 (8.0)	17 (68.0)(2; 11.8)	13	6 (46.2)	3 (23.1)	4 (30.8)(1; 25.0)	

(*) Lung cancer cases are shown in bold for each category together with the risk as a percentage.

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t003

Table 4. Analysis of the radiation exposure (mean, minimum, maximum) associated with the management of SPN for chest radiograph according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

Intervention	N (%)	Total (mSv)	Cancer (mSv)	No cancer (mSv)	p-value
Follow-up					
x-ray	35 (41.7)	3.2 (0.2–28.2)	7.2 (7.2–7.2)	3.0 (0.2–28.2)	0.071
CT	48 (57.1)	15.0 (7.1–60.1)	32.1 (32.1–32.1)	14.2 (7.1–60.1)	0.363
PET/CT	1 (1.2)	39.1 (39.1–39.1)	-	39.1 (39.1–39.1)	-
Total	84 (17.5)	10.3 (0.2–60.1)	19.7 (7.2–32.1)	9.9 (0.2–60.1)	0.027
Immediate intervention					
x-ray	67 (22.3)	1.7 (0.2–14.2)	-	1.7 (0.2–14.2)	-
CT	225 (74.8)	14.0 (7.1–60.1)	19.3 (7.1–39.1)	13.1 (7.1–60.1)	0.099
PET/CT	9 (3.0)	26.3 (25.1–28.1)	25.9 (25.1–27.1)	26.7 (25.1–28.1)	0.444
Total	301 (62.7)	11.6 (0.2–60.1)	10.4 (7.1–39.1)	20.3 (0.2–60.1)	0.003
TOTAL	480 (100.0)	9.1 (0.1–60.1)	20.3 (7.1–39.1)	8.1 (0.1–60.1)	<0.001

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t004

Table 5. Analysis of the radiation exposure (mean, minimum, maximum) associated with the management of SPN for CT according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

Intervention	N (%)	Total (mSv)	Cancer (mSv)	No cancer (mSv)	p-value
Follow-up					
- x-ray	18 (9.2)	12.2 (7.1–28.1)	-	12.2 (7.1–28.1)	-
- CT	175 (89.3)	25.5 (14.0–81.0)	33.1 (14.0–49.0)	25.0 (14.0–81.0)	0.018
- PET/CT	3 (1.5)	34.3 (32.0–39.0)	32.0 (32.0–32.0)	36.5 (32.0–39.0)	0.999
- Total	196 (47.5)	24.4 (7.1–81.0)	33.0 (14.0–49.0)	23.9 (7.1–81.0)	0.178
Immediate intervention					
- x-ray	3 (2.7)	20.0 (14.0–32.0)	-	20.0 (14.0–32.0)	-
- CT	20 (18.3)	18.0 (7.0–53.0)	19.5 (7.0–32.0)	17.8 (7.0–53.0)	0.999
- PET/CT	47 (43.1)	36.3 (32.0–53.0)	32.0 (32.0–32.0)	38.8 (32.0–53.0)	<0.001
- Biopsy	39 (35.8)	14.0 (7.0–53.0)	9.2 (7.0–46.0)	18.1 (7.0–53.0)	0.147
- Total	109 (26.4)	24.5 (7.0–53.0)	20.2 (7.0–46.0)	26.7 (7.0–53.0)	<0.001
TOTAL	305 (100.0)	19.9 (7.0–81.0)	23.1 (7.0–49.0)	19.5 (7.0–81.0)	0.038

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t005

Table 6. Analysis of the number of imaging tests (mean, minimum, maximum) associated with the management of SPN for chest radiograph according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

Intervention	N (%)	Total	Cancer	No cancer	p-value
Follow-up					
- x-ray	35 (41.7)	1.4 (1.0–2.0)	1.5 (1.0–2.0)	1.4 (1.0–2.0)	0.733
- CT	48 (57.1)	1.2 (0–5.0)	1.0 (1.0–1.0)	1.2 (0.0–5.0)	0.736
- PET/CT	1 (1.2)	0.1 (0–1.0)	0.5 (0–1.0)	0.1 (0.0–1.0)	<0.001
- Total	84 (17.5)	2.8 (2.0–8.0)	3.8 (3.0–4.0)	2.7 (2.0–8.0)	0.085
Immediate intervention					
- x-ray	67 (22.3)	1.2 (1.0–2.0)	1.0 (1.0–1.0)	1.3 (1.0–2.0)	0.001
- CT	225 (74.8)	1.2 (0–6.0)	1.5 (0–4.0)	1.2 (0–6.0)	0.087
- PET/CT	9 (3.0)	0.1 (0–1.0)	0.3 (0–1.0)	0.1 (0–1.0)	0.001
- Total	301 (62.7)	2.7 (2.0–7.0)	3.4 (2.0–5.0)	2.6 (2.0–7.0)	<0.001

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t006

Table 7. Analysis of the number of imaging tests (mean, minimum, maximum) associated with the management of SPN for CT according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

Intervention	N (%)	Total	Cancer	No cancer	p-value
Follow-up					
- x-ray	18 (9.2)	0.1 (0–1.0)	0	0.1 (0–1.0)	0.280
- CT	175 (89.3)	3.2 (1.0–8.0)	3.3 (1.0–7.0)	3.2 (1.0–8.0)	0.946
- PET/CT	3 (1.5)	0.1 (0–1.0)	0.5 (0–1.0)	0.1 (0–1.0)	<0.001
- Total	196 (47.5)	3.5 (2.0–9.0)	4.6 (3.0–7.0)	3.4 (2.0–9.0)	0.009
Immediate intervention					
- x-ray	3 (2.7)	0 (0–1.0)	0	0 (0–1.0)	0.212
- CT	20 (18.3)	1.7 (1.0–5.0)	1.1 (1.0–3.0)	2.0 (1.0–5.0)	<0.001
- PET/CT	47 (43.1)	0.6 (0–1.0)	0.5 (0–1.0)	0.6 (0–1.0)	0.491
- Total	109 (26.4)	3.0 (2.0–6.0)	2.6 (2.0–5.0)	3.1 (2.0–6.0)	0.021

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158458.t007

ultimately diagnosed with cancer underwent a significantly lower number of imaging studies (2.6 vs 3.1, $p = 0.021$) (Table 7).

In S1 and S2 Tables, we show the analysis of the radiation exposure (total) associated with the management of SPN for both chest radiograph and CT according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

Discussion

In this study, we describe the different management strategies of SPN when first detected either on chest radiograph or on CT in the usual care setting, their relationship with lung cancer diagnosis and the radiation exposure associated during follow-up of 18 months.

More than 20% of patients with SPN detected on either chest radiograph (19.8%) or CT (26.1%) did not have additional interventions and none of them developed lung cancer (100% negative predictive value). Hence, in contrast with previous studies [13], the patients included in our study did not appear to have received less evaluation than they should. Out of 480 patients with SPN detected on chest radiograph 346 (72.0%), and 254 (61.5%) of the 413 patients with SPN detected on CT, had additional diagnostic tests and were not diagnosed with lung cancer.

Those patients with a SPN initially detected on either chest radiograph or CT, who were followed up, underwent a high number of CTs during the 18 month follow-up period (patients with SPN initially detected on CT underwent a maximum of 8 CTs and those with SPN initially detected on chest radiograph underwent a maximum of 5 CTs). According to Fleischner recommendations, these patients had more CTs than should have been done, conferring more radiation exposure. Previous studies also have presented an excess of invasive procedures in patients with a benign nodule showing that clinicians seem to be unaware that nodule management guidelines exist, or just do not to follow them [15].

Overall, patients with SPN detected on CT received 19.9 mSv radiation exposure per capita during the 18 months of follow-up. Moreover, the maximum radiation dose per capita received during this period of time was 81.0 mSv. Therefore, these results showed a relevant associated radiation exposure, given that the epidemiological data directly suggest an increased cancer risk in the 10 mSv to 100 mSv range [24]. A previous study showed 0.7% incidence of cancer and 1% mortality attributable to imaging tests during a period of 22 years.

The increase in the use of medical imaging in clinical practice [25] fuels concern about radiation exposure and cumulative risk of cancer [26]. In fact, in 2013 the European Union legislation set out a series of directives regarding radiation protection and included the safe use of

ionizing radiation in medical practice [27]. One key innovation is the need to record the radiation dose received by each patient undergoing a medical imaging test involving x rays, particularly CT, in order to reduce unnecessary exposure to radiation. Hence, clinicians have a key role in controlling the effective dose received by each patient during the management of SPN and limiting the number of CTs following available guidelines.

However, the increasing availability of machines capable of iterative reconstruction are likely to decrease the radiation exposure significantly. Some authors have demonstrated that low dose scans are acceptable and do not result in changes of nodule volume [28]. Chest radiographs are usually chosen for surveillance in order to limit radiation exposure, and according to these data this approach could lead to low effective doses.

The variables associated with a higher probability of having immediate interventions were for both chest radiograph and CT nodule spiculated borders and size above 8 mm and for chest radiographs also the patients' sex. Women who had a chest radiograph were less likely to have immediate interventions than men, because lung cancer used to be thought of as a man's disease, given that the smoking status is more frequent in men than in women. In contrast with previous studies, smoking habit was not a factor influencing immediate interventions. Maybe, the high number of not available data in this variable could explain this fact.

Fleischner recommendations [11], state that although in low-risk patients follow-up of SPN ≤ 4 mm is not needed, low- and high-risk patients with SPN > 4 mm should be followed. In our study, out of 47 patients with SPN ≤ 4 mm detected on CT, 33 (70.2%) had either follow-up or additional interventions, and none of them were diagnosed of lung cancer (approximately half of them were categorized as low-risk patients –data not shown–). Moreover, 88 patients with nodules > 4 mm detected on CT did not have further testing and none of them were diagnosed with lung cancer. When both management and lung cancer diagnosis were analysed for the cut-off 5 mm (according to BTS guidelines [10] and the latest information from the Nelson trial [12]), only 4 (4.4%) patients were diagnosed of lung cancer. Thus, these results could support that the 4mm recommended by Fleischner is probably too low. Our results would confirm the appropriateness of the new established criteria.

The American College of Chest Physicians [16] and the BTS [10] recommended that in patients with SPN > 8 mm in diameter, clinicians should estimate the pretest probability of malignancy using for example the Brock model [29]. In our study, in those patients who had a CT, only radiographic characteristics (size and border) were associated with a higher probability of having immediate interventions. However, although clinicians did not follow-up the majority of the established recommendations, patients did not seem to receive under-evaluation; in contrast, a significant number of the patients received an excessive amount of interventions when compared to guideline recommendations. Moreover, given the long time until the diagnosis was ascertained in some cases, an effort should be made in the improvement of the quality of care reducing anxiety to patients.

The independent risk factors for malignancy included in the available recommendations are slightly different from those identified in our study [21]. Thus, large series of nodules in low risk population will probably need guidelines adapted to routine clinical care.

Nodule follow-up was heterogeneous and perhaps standardizing the approach to SPN follow up, would be to review these patients in a multidisciplinary meeting including both pulmonologists and radiologists.

Our patients were followed during 18 months due to financial reasons. This could seem short to be certain about the diagnosis in smaller nodules. Since evidence of malignant disease for at least 2 years is a reliable indicator of a benign process [30], some of the patients could have developed the disease in the following years. However, we believe that given the natural history of lung cancer, the management of SPN during 18 months is essential in the prognosis

of a patient. Lung cancer could be present without having been diagnosed, but it could be unethical to carry out new diagnostic procedures in patients without a clinical suspicion. Nevertheless, none of the patients were lost at follow-up. The high percentage of non-interventions for CT and chest radiograph could suggest a high number of benign features, which would not reflect the real-world clinical dilemma. However, benign lesions, intrapulmonary lymph and pseudolesions, when detected, were excluded from our study.

Conclusions

Our results show the different SPN management procedures in the usual care setting. Patients who did not have additional interventions were not diagnosed with lung cancer. However, there was an excessive amount of interventions in a high percentage of patients presenting SPN, which was associated with an excess of radiation exposure.

Supporting Information

S1 Fig. Management strategies carried out in patients having SPN for chest radiography and the detailed description of the diagnostic pathway.

(TIF)

S2 Fig. Management strategies carried out in patients having SPN for CT and the detailed description of the diagnostic pathway.

(TIF)

S1 Table. Analysis of the radiation exposure (total) associated with the management of SPN for chest radiograph according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

(DOC)

S2 Table. Analysis of the radiation exposure (total) associated with the management of SPN for CT according to the management strategy and for patients with a final diagnosis of lung cancer and those without it.

(DOC)

S1 Text. Management strategies carried out in patients having SPN for chest radiography and the detailed description of the diagnostic pathway.

(DOC)

S2 Text. Management strategies carried out in patients having SPN for CT and the detailed description of the diagnostic pathway.

(DOCX)

Author Contributions

Conceived and designed the experiments: BL IHA JV IGA. Performed the experiments: BL IGA JV MFL MLD MPV NGS. Analyzed the data: BL NGS. Wrote the paper: BL IGA JV MFL MLD MPV NGS.

References

1. Swensen SJ, Silverstein MD, Ilstrup DM, Schleck CD, Edell ES. The probability of malignancy in solitary pulmonary nodules. Application to small radiologically indeterminate nodules. *Arch Intern Med.* 1997; 157: 849–55. PMID: [9129544](#)
2. Mold JW, Stein HF. The cascade effect in the clinical care of patients. *N Engl J Med.* 1986; 314: 512–4. PMID: [3945278](#)

3. Deyo RA. Cascade effects of medical technology. *Annu Rev Public Health*. 2002; 23: 23–44. PMID: [11910053](#)
4. Lumberras B, González-Alvárez I, Lorente MF, Calbo J, Aranaz J, Hernández-Aguado I. Unexpected findings at imaging: predicting frequency in various types of studies. *Eur J Radiol*. 2010; 74: 269–749.
5. Lumberras B, Donat L, Hernández-Aguado I. Incidental findings in imaging diagnostic tests: a systematic review. *Br J Radiol*. 2010; 83: 276–89 doi: [10.1259/bjr/98067945](#) PMID: [20335439](#)
6. Fisher ES, Welch HG. Avoiding the unintended consequences of growth in medical care. *JAMA*. 1999; 281: 446–53. PMID: [9952205](#)
7. Berlin L. Potential legal ramifications of whole-body CT screening: taking a peek into Pandora's box. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2003; 180: 317–22 PMID: [12540423](#)
8. Hansell DM, Bankier AA, MacMahon H, McLoud TC, Müller NL, Remy J. Fleischner Society: glossary of terms for thoracic imaging. *Radiology*. 2008; 246: 697–722. doi: [10.1148/radiol.2462070712](#) PMID: [18195376](#)
9. Swensen SJ, Silverstein MD, Edell ES, Trastek VF, Aughenbaugh GL, Ilstrup DM et al. Solitary pulmonary nodules: clinical prediction model versus physicians. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 1999; 74: 319–29 PMID: [10221459](#)
10. Callister ME, Baldwin DR, Akram AR, Barnard S, Cane P, Draffan J et al; British Thoracic Society Pulmonary Nodule Guideline Development Group; British Thoracic Society Standards of Care Committee. British Thoracic Society guidelines for the investigation and management of pulmonary nodules. *Thorax*. 2015; 70 Suppl 2: ii1–ii54. doi: [10.1136/thoraxjnl-2015-207168](#) PMID: [26082159](#)
11. MacMahon H, Austin JH, Gamsu G, Herold CJ, Jett JR, Naidich DP; Fleischner Society. Guidelines for management of small pulmonary nodules detected on CT scans: a statement from the Fleischner Society. *Radiology*. 2005; 237: 395–400. PMID: [16244247](#)
12. Horeweg N, van Rosmalen J, Heuvelmans MA, van der Aalst CM, Vliegenthart R, Scholten ET et al. Lung cancer probability in patients with CT-detected pulmonary nodules: a prespecified analysis of data from the NELSON trial of low-dose CT screening. *Lancet Oncol*. 2014; 15: 1332–41. doi: [10.1016/S1470-2045\(14\)70389-4](#) PMID: [25282285](#)
13. Wiener RS, Gould MK, Slatore CG, Fincke BG, Schwartz LM, Woloshin S. Resource use and guideline concordance in evaluation of pulmonary nodules for cancer: too much and too little care. *JAMA Intern Med*. 2014; 174: 871–80. doi: [10.1001/jamainternmed.2014.561](#) PMID: [24710850](#)
14. Alzahouri K, Velten M, Arveux P, Woronoff-Lemsi MC, Jolly D, Guillemin F. Management of SPN in France. Pathways for definitive diagnosis of solitary pulmonary nodule: a multicentre study in 18 French districts. *BMC Cancer*. 2008; 8: 93. doi: [10.1186/1471-2407-8-93](#) PMID: [18402653](#)
15. Tanner NT, Aggarwal J, Gould MK, Kearney P, Diette G, Vachani A, Fang KC, Silvestri GA. Management of Pulmonary Nodules by Community Pulmonologists: A Multicenter Observational Study. *Chest*. 2015; 148: 1405–1414. doi: [10.1378/chest.15-0630](#) PMID: [26087071](#)
16. Hansell DM, Bankier AA, MacMahon H, McLoud TC, Müller NL, Remy J. Fleischner Society: glossary of terms for thoracic imaging. *Radiology*. 2008; 246: 697–722. doi: [10.1148/radiol.2462070712](#) PMID: [18195376](#)
17. Gould MK, Fletcher J, Iannettoni MD, Lynch WR, Midthun DE, Naidich DP et al; American College of Chest Physicians. Evaluation of patients with pulmonary nodules: when is it lung cancer?: ACCP evidence-based clinical practice guidelines (2nd edition). *Chest*. 2007; 132: 108S–130S PMID: [17873164](#)
18. Gould MK, Donington J, Lynch WR, Mazzone PJ, Midthun DE, Naidich DP et al. Evaluation of individuals with pulmonary nodules: when is it lung cancer? Diagnosis and management of lung cancer, 3rd ed: American College of Chest Physicians evidence-based clinical practice guidelines. *Chest*. 2013; 143: e93S–120S
19. Aberle DR, DeMello S, Berg CD, Black WC, Brewer B, Church TR et al; National Lung Screening Trial Research Team. Results of the two incidence screenings in the National Lung Screening Trial. *N Engl J Med*. 2013; 369: 920–31 doi: [10.1056/NEJMoa1208962](#) PMID: [24004119](#)
20. Gómez-Sáez N, Hernández-Aguado I, Vilar J, González-Alvarez I, Lorente MF, Domingo ML et al. Lung cancer risk and cancer-specific mortality in subjects undergoing routine imaging test when stratified with and without identified lung nodule on imaging study. *Eur Radiol*. 2015; 25: 3518–27. doi: [10.1007/s00330-015-3775-3](#) PMID: [25953000](#)
21. Gómez-Sáez N, González-Álvarez I, Vilar J, Hernández-Aguado I, Domingo ML, Lorente MF et al. Prevalence and variables associated with solitary pulmonary nodules in a routine clinic-based population: a cross-sectional study. *Eur Radiol*. 2014; 24: 2174–82. doi: [10.1007/s00330-014-3249-z](#) PMID: [24962823](#)
22. Fritz A, Percy C, Jack A et al, eds. International classification of diseases for oncology. 3rd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2000.

23. Mettler FA Jr, Huda W, Yoshizumi TT, Mahesh M. Effective doses in radiology and diagnostic nuclear medicine: a catalog. *Radiology*. 2008; 248: 254–6350. doi: [10.1148/radiol.2481071451](https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2481071451) PMID: [18566177](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18566177/)
24. Lin EC. Radiation risk from medical imaging. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 2010; 85: 1142–6. doi: [10.4065/mcp.2010.0260](https://doi.org/10.4065/mcp.2010.0260) PMID: [21123642](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21123642/)
25. Bhargavan M. Trends in the utilization of medical procedures that use ionizing radiation. *Health Phys* 2008; 95:612–627
26. Einstein AJ, Henzlova MJ, Rajagopalan S. Estimating risk of cancer associated with radiation exposure from 64-slice computed tomography coronary angiography. *JAMA* 2007; 298:317–323 PMID: [17635892](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17635892/)
27. European Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom on basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation and repealing Directives 89/618/Euratom, 90/641/Euratom, 96/29/Euratom, 97/43/Euratom and 2003/122/Euratom. *OJ of the EU*. L13; 57: 1–73 (2014).
28. Hein PA, Romano VC, Rogalla P, Klessen C, Lembcke A, Bornemann L et al. Variability of semiautomated lung nodule volumetry on ultralow-dose CT: comparison with nodule volumetry on standard-dose CT. *J Digit Imaging*. 2010; 23: 8–17. doi: [10.1007/s10278-008-9157-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10278-008-9157-5) PMID: [18773240](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18773240/)
29. Al-Ameri A, Malhotra P, Thygesen H, Plant PK, Vaidyanathan S, Karthik S et al. Risk of malignancy in pulmonary nodules: A validation study of four prediction models. *Lung Cancer*. 2015; 89: 27–30. doi: [10.1016/j.lungcan.2015.03.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lungcan.2015.03.018) PMID: [25864782](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25864782/)
30. Viggiano RW, Swensen SJ, Rosenow EC 3rd. Evaluation and management of solitary and multiple pulmonary nodules. *Clin Chest Med* 1992; 13:83–95. PMID: [1582151](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1582151/)